

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DYSFUNCTION OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract

The presented data of a clinical examination of 22 patients with pain dysfunction syndrome of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) indicate that in 30.8% of them the cause of the pathology is a violation of functional occlusion. The treatment of such patients is complex, phased and includes drug therapy, physiotherapy, orthopedic methods: treatment with caps, selective grinding of teeth, rational prosthetics.

Keywords: *TMJ dysfunctions, functional occlusion.*

Occlusal disorders are of great importance in the etiology and pathogenesis of the syndrome of TMJ dysfunction from incongruent articular surfaces, the connection is unstable. Occlusion is a stabilizing factor next to the intraarticular disc, ligamentous-capsular apparatus, and muscular corset - multiple, symmetrical, point fissure-hilly closure of the dentition [3,4]. Therefore, any violation of functional occlusion can lead to negative changes in the functional state of the masticatory muscles, dispositions of the lower jaw, and relationships and anatomical safety of its elements [1,2]. It is obvious that the combination of endocrine and psycho-emotional pathologies that affect the level of adaptive capabilities of the body to adverse conditions, violations of functional occlusion, are the trigger for the development of the TMJ pain dysfunction syndrome.

Purpose of the study: based on the data of anamnesis and clinical and laboratory studies of patients, to establish the causes leading to the appearance of occlusion-articulation syndrome of TMJ dysfunction and to outline a set of orthopedic dental measures for the treatment of the above pathology.

Material and research methods. The clinical examination covered

collection of complaints and anamnesis, as well as a detailed functional examination - a review of the face, cephalometry, checking the mobility of the lower jaw, palpation of the masticatory muscles, clinical examination of occlusion. For a more detailed examination of the nature of the closure of the dentition in the position of habitual occlusion, anterior and lateral, the features of articulation were studied on diagnostic models of the jaws in an articulator debugged for individual work.

Results and discussion. 22 patients (14 women, 8 men) aged 20 to 50 years with symptoms of TMJ dysfunction were asked to the clinic of orthopedic dentistry for medical help and were clinically examined. Pain syndrome of varying strength forced the patients to seek help. Patients complained of constant, constricted or boring one- or two-sided pain in the parotid-masticatory area with irradiation in the temple, jaw, teeth, cheekbones, headaches, pain in the ears. As a rule, patients were emotionally excited, seeking help - they were nervous, crying, emotionally portraying their feelings. On examination of 26 (22) patients with TMJ pain dysfunction syndrome, functional occlusion disorders were found in 6 individuals (27.27%) due to: - increased abrasion of hard tissues teeth against the background of parafunctional activity of masticatory muscles, which led to a loss of occlusal height, the appearance of unstable occlusal contacts in the position of the central ratio, supracontacts during laterotrusion, protrusion movements of the lower jaw;

- deformations of the occlusal surface of the dentition due to carious destruction and partial loss of teeth. Disturbances in articulatory balance led to the movement of teeth towards the existing defects, and therefore, to the appearance of supracontacts in centric and eccentric occlusions;

- errors in the process of orthopedic treatment, namely: fixation on prostheses of the previous usual forced position of the jaws, formed as a result of violations of functional occlusion and disposition of the lower jaw that existed before prosthetics; incorrect formation of the occlusal surface of artificial crowns and bridges, the appearance of unstable occlusion, supracontacts;

- errors of orthodontic treatment. The change in occlusal relationships led to mandibular dispositions and intra-articular disorders.

Patients were treated in several stages. At the first stage, the pain syndrome was eliminated by creating conditions for relaxing the masticatory muscles. To eliminate the pain syndrome, a complex of therapeutic measures was used: medication, physiotherapy and treatment with caps. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and analgesics (Meloxicam, Ketanov) were prescribed, including in the form of ointment dressings in the parotid-masticatory area based on ibuprofen, butadione. As part of the complex therapy, calcium, iron, vitamins of group B, C, folic acid were prescribed, which affect the metabolic processes of nerve and muscle cells, eliminate induration and muscle soreness, and reduce the irritability of trigger points. Sedative drugs were prescribed to relieve psycho-emotional stress and improve sleep vegetable origin. Physiotherapeutic procedures included massage, myogymnastics, pulsed current, electro-, ultraphonophoresis for 10-15 procedures. To relax the muscles, deprogramming their work at the first stage, relaxation plates with clamp fixation and a bite pad behind the upper incisors were used. The bite pad behind the upper incisors was in contact with the lower incisors, creating deocclusion of the lateral teeth by 1-2 mm, which helped to turn off the effect of the supracontacts of the contacts on the forced position of the lower jaw, relax the muscles and self-center the articular heads in the articular fossae. It was recommended to wear the plate for two weeks (to avoid protrusion of the lateral teeth), constantly, always at night. The plate was corrected after 1, 3 days, 1, 2 weeks. Patients indicated a weakening of pain and tension in the masticatory muscles after a few days. At the second stage, the central ratio of the jaws was determined and fixed. After the pain syndrome was relieved, it became possible to find and fix the "healing, comfortable" position of the lower jaw for the TMJ, which does not depend on the existing occlusal contacts, but is limited by the anatomical shape of the TMJ, its connected-capsular apparatus. To determine the central ratio, manual techniques were used, including the orientation of the lower jaw during swallowing movements. To fix the central ratio, bite plates made of refractory wax were used, thermoplastic plates, occlusal A - silicone, and in the absence of a large number of teeth - hard bases with wax bite rollers. At the third stage, the lower jaw was fixed in a "treatment" position using stabilizing, repositioning caps. Determining and fixing the central ratio of the jaw model was carefully studied in the articulator, planned and carried out selective teeth polishing, burl structures were made. Stabilizing caps covered the occlusal surface of all teeth and provided point contact only with the supporting tubercles of the opposite jaw.

The anterior teeth were in contact with the cap only when the teeth were strongly compressed. In the area of the lateral teeth, the cap had an occlusal thickness of 1.5-2 mm. On the mouthguard, "fangs guidance" was created with laterotrusion contacts, incisors with protrusion movements of the lower jaw, while excluding contacts of the lateral teeth. Such structural features of the stabilizing splints contributed to muscle relaxation and self-centering of the articular heads in the physiological position. According to the integrity of the dentition, the mouthguards were mainly made for the

lower jaw, since it had advantages in aesthetics, phonetics, and was easier to manufacture. In the absence of teeth on one jaw, the mouthguard was installed on the jaw with defects in the dentition, while it took the form of a mouthguard-prosthesis. Quite often, the choice of jaw for the installation of a mouth guard depended on the inclination of the upper incisors. Along their vestibular edge, an inclined mouthguard was installed on the upper jaw, which made it possible to reproduce a functional surface on the mouthguard and provide an effective sagittal incisive path with a gentle start of movement of the lower incisors along the palatal surface of the upper jaws and deocclusion of the lateral teeth. Due to the sheer or retrusion position of the upper incisors, the mouthguard was installed on the lower jaw with obligatory grinding of the vestibular-cutting edge of the mouthguard in the area of the lower incisors to prevent the appearance of supracontacts during protrusion movements of the lower jaw. 6 months. For dispositions of the lower jaw, repositioning caps with deep imprints of antagonist teeth on the occlusal surface were used, which made it possible to keep the lower jaw in the "treatment" position. occlusal relationships in both centric and eccentric occlusions. Often, the final prosthesis was preceded by temporary structures, on which the occlusal relationships were corrected. The prostheses were made using semi-adjustable articulators, making it possible to set the position of the upper jaw and reproduce the movements of the lower jaw, identical to those in the patient.

Conclusions

1. According to our observations, functional occlusion disorders were found in about 30.8% of patients with TMJ pain dysfunction syndrome.

2. The cause of violations of occlusal relationships is the pathological processes of the dentition, their morphological and functional complications, as well as iatrogenic factors

3. Violation of functional occlusion on the endocrine and background background. psycho-emotional pathology lead to the emergence of a syndrome of pain dysfunction of the TMJ.

4. Treatment of patients with occlusion-articulation syndrome of TMJ dysfunction should be comprehensive, multi-stage and include drug therapy, physiotherapy, treatment with caps to normalize occlusal relationships and the functional state of masticatory muscles, rational prosthetics

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